

Synthesis of New 5-Substituted Oxazolophenoxazine Derivatives

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2-Aryl-5H-oxazolo (4, 5-b) phenoxazine derivatives (I) Ar = C₆H₅-, p-CH₃O-C₆H₄ reacts with 5-chloro acetyloxazolophenoxazine derivatives (II) which interacts readily with amines and hydrazine. The hydrazinoacetyl oxazolophenoxazine derivatives (V) on condensation with aldehydes give new Schiff bases (VII).

It is well known that oxazoles find extensive uses as optical brightness¹, dyes² and their intermediate used as photographic sensitizers³. A large number of these compounds have pharmacological effect⁴ and several aliphatic oxazoles have been prepared as potential local anaesthetics⁵.

In view of the remarkable antibacterial⁶ and antifungal⁷ activity of oxazolophenoxazine derivatives, this paper aims at the synthesis of a number of new 5-substituted oxazolophenoxazine derivatives. Thus, when 2-aryl-5H-oxazolo (4,5-b) phenoxazine derivatives (I) reacted with chloroacetyl chloride in dry toluene gave 5-chloroacetyl oxazolophenoxazine derivatives⁸ (II) in good yields.

- Ia. Ar = C₆H₅-
b. Ar = p-CH₃O-C₆H₄-

(II) Reacted readily with secondary amines, morpholine, piperidine, anisidine and ephedrine in

toluene giving the corresponding glycyloxazolophenoxazine derivative (IIIa-d).

- IIIa. R = piperidino
b. R = morpholino
c. R = p-CH₃O-C₆H₄NH-
d. R = ephedrine.

II(a, b; 2 moles) also reacted with piperazine giving 5,5'-piperazino-bis(methylenecarbonyl) dioxazolophenoxazine derivatives (IV).

- IVa. Ar = C₆H₅-
b. Ar = p-CH₃O-C₆H₄-

The structures of III and IV have been established by their analytical data and their IR spectra (>C=O; 1700-1685 cm⁻¹). Equimolecular quantities of (II) and hydrazine hydrate reacted in ethanol to give 5-(hydrazinoacetyl) oxazolophenoxazine (V).

The IR spectrum of this compound showed absorption bands at 1700 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$) group and 3380 cm^{-1} (NH) group. Further condensation of two

moles of II (Ar = C_6H_5 ; $CH_3O-C_6H_4-$) with one mole of hydrazine hydrate furnished, 5,5'- hydrazine-bis(methylenecarbonyl) dioxazolo[4,5-b]phenoxazine (VI) in 60-65% yield.

Condensation of (V) with aldehydes in glacial acetic acid furnished the Schiff bases VII.

- VIIa. R = C_6H_5-
 b. R = $p-CH_3O.C_6H_4-$
 c. R = $o-OH; C_6H_4-$
 d. R = $p-(CH_3)_2NC_6H_4-$
 e. R = Ferrocenyl ($C_5H_5FeC_5H_4-$)

The structures of these compounds were established by their analytical and IR spectral data which showed absorption bands at 1620 cm^{-1} ($>C=N$), 1695 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$) and 3350 cm^{-1} NH stretching frequency.

Experimental

Infrared spectra were determined in KBr pellets on unicam sp. 200 G infrared spectrophotometer. All melting points are uncorrected.

2-Aryl-5H-oxazolo (4,5-b) phenoxazines (I:a, b)

Pure 3-aminophenoxaz-2-one (0.1 mol) was refluxed for 7 hr with the aromatic aldehydes (0.1 mol) in

presence of excess glacial acetic acid and piperidine (0.05 mol). The reaction mixture was cooled, the deposited solid after triturating with a small amount of alcohol was filtered, washed several times with alcohol and crystallized from the proper solvents (Ia m.p. 275° ; Ib m.p. 250°)⁹.

5-Chloroacetyloxazolo[4,5-b]phenoxazines⁸ (III)

Chloroacetylchloride (0.01 mol) was added slowly to oxazolo[4,5-b]phenoxazine (0.015 mol) in dry toluene (150 ml) and the reaction mixture refluxed for 3 hrs. Toluene was removed under reduced pressure the residue was filtered off and then crystallized from alcohol.

Glycylloxazolo[4,5-b]phenoxazine derivatives (IIIa-d)

A mixture of I(a,b; 0.01 mol) and the appropriate base (0.03 mol) in 20 ml of dry toluene was refluxed

for 3 hr. The amine hydrochloride was filtered off, the organic layer extracted with 1N HCl ($3 \times 30\text{ ml}$), and the acidic extract neutralized with sodium carbonate solution. The precipitated solid was collected, washed with sodium carbonate solution and then crystallized from alcohol-benzene mixture to give IIIa-d. Table 1 represents the physical and analytical data of the compounds IIIa-d.

5,5'-piperazine-bis(methylene carbonyl) dioxazolo[4,5-b]phenoxazine (IV)

By reacting II(a,b; 0.02 mol) with piperazine (0.01 mol) following the procedure outlined above, and the pale yellow products which separated out were crystallized from alcohol to give IV in 59-63% yields. IVa m.p. 221° found: N, 11.21%. $C_{46}H_{34}N_6O_8$ reqd. N, 10.98%. IVb m.p. $260-1^\circ$ found: N, 10.54%. $C_{48}H_{38}N_6O_8$ reqd. N, 10.16%. These compounds gave satisfactory C, H analysis.

5-(Hydrazinoacetyl) oxazolo[4,5-b]phenoxazine (V)

A mixture of II(a,b; 0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (99-100%; 0.05 mol) in 15 ml of ethanol was refluxed for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool, diluted with water and crystallized from ethanol-water to give pale yellow needles of (V) in 60-70% yield. Va, mp. $300-1^\circ$, found: N, 15.13%. $C_{21}H_{18}N_4O_3$ reqd. N, 15.05%. Vb, m.p. 230° (decomp); found: N, 13.97%. $C_{22}H_{18}N_4O_4$ reqd. N, 14.00%.

5,5' Hydrazino-bis(methylenecarbonyl) dioxazolo[4,5-b]phenoxazine (VI)

A mixture of II(a,b; 0.02 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in 20 ml of ethanol was refluxed

TABLE 1—5-GLYCYLOXAZOLOPHENOXAZINE DERIVATIVES

Comp. III No.	Ar	Yield %	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	Found % N	Reqd. % N
a	C ₆ H ₅ - p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	80	205-7	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₃	9.76	9.88
		82	243-4	C ₂₇ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₄	9.54	9.23
b	C ₆ H ₅ - p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	79	185-6	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	9.72	9.84
		75	215-17	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₅	9.09	9.19
c	C ₆ H ₅ - p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	70	206	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	9.13	9.07
		85	217-18	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₅	8.66	8.51
d	C ₆ H ₅ - p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	80	279-80	C ₃₁ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₄	8.41	8.32
		76	220-1	C ₃₂ H ₂₉ N ₃ O ₅	7.99	7.85

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H analysis.

TABLE 2

Comp. VII No.	Ar.	Yield %	M.P. °C	Mol. formula	Found % N	Reqd. % N
a	C ₆ H ₅ - p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	65	298-9	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃	12.23	12.17
		67	245-6	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄	11.66	11.42
b	C ₆ H ₅ - p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	70	300-1	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄	11.75	11.42
		72	247-8	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₅	10.57	10.77
c	C ₆ H ₅ - p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	71	290-1	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₅	11.54	11.81
		77	249-50	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₅	10.97	11.07
d	C ₆ H ₅ - p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	65	305-6	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₅ O ₃	14.05	13.91
		68	252-3	C ₃₁ H ₂₈ N ₅ O ₄	13.25	13.13
e	C ₆ H ₅ - p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	70	240-1	C ₃₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₃ Fe	10.02	9.85
		78	300 dec.	C ₃₃ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄ Fe	9.47	9.36

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H analysis.

for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and the precipitated solid filtered, washed with cold water and crystallized from ethanol to give VI in 60-65% yield VIa, m.p. 200; found: N, 12.01%, C₄₂H₂₈N₆O₈ reqd. N, 11.79%. VIb, m.p. 221°-12°; found: N, 11.50%, C₄₄H₃₂N₆O₈ reqd. N, 11.35%.

Condensation of 5-(hydrazinoacetyl) oxazolophenoxazine with aldehydes and formation of (VI)

A solution of equimolecular quantities of (V) and the appropriate aldehyde in glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 2-3 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured onto crushed ice and the deposited solid was collected, washed several times with cold water and then crystallized from alcohol to give

pale green products of VII(a-e). Table 2 represents the physical and analytical data of VII.

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